

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH ONLINE DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study, titled "Lived Experiences of University Students in Learning Online During the Covid-19 Pandemic," aimed to explore the significant challenges faced by students in learning English and the coping mechanisms they employed when in-person learning was strictly limited. The study employed purposive sampling to select 12 respondents and utilized in-depth interviews and focus group discussions as the primary data collection methods. To interpret the results, the six-step process developed by Braun and Clarke (2006) was used. Thematic analysis revealed that learning English online during the Covid-19 pandemic, respondents encountered challenges such as incompatibility of learning devices, unstable internet connectivity, inappropriate places of study, too much homework from teachers, teacher's lack of preparation, mental and physical health problems. To cope with these difficulties, the respondents employed various strategies to adapt to the new learning environment. These strategies included upgrading their mobile devices, maintaining frequent communication with teachers and classmates, requesting extensions for assignment due dates, participating in group study sessions, improving self-discipline, and finding suitable study locations.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic, Lived experiences, Online learning

INTRODUCTION

English holds a significant position in contemporary society and education, particularly in tertiary education across various countries, including Thailand. It serves as a vital tool for students to access scientific knowledge in their respective fields of study. When completing assignments, research, and projects, students rely on English resources and data to acquire the necessary information. In addition, when students opt for pursuing degree programs overseas, English is commonly selected as the primary language of instruction in foreign universities. Proficiency in English also enhances graduates' prospects of securing desirable employment opportunities in reputable companies. This proficiency enables them to efficiently access information from international sources, utilize foreign websites, engage in business activities, and communicate with other foreign companies (Al-Khalil, 2015).

English language instruction is constantly evolving in the 21st century, especially in conjunction with technological advancements. The rise of mobile technology and widespread use of smartphones has allowed individuals to access the internet and a wide range of mobile applications wherever they go. This accessibility to apps benefits language learners as well. Furthermore, teachers can enhance their teaching knowledge and skills by engaging with podcasts, webinars, and recorded videos of talks delivered by other educators. Teachers utilize social media platforms to establish communication channels that extend beyond the traditional classroom setting. Moreover, the ability to engage in face-to-face online interactions with students has created a new market for online classes, presenting additional opportunities for teachers (Chong, 2016).

Online learning possesses distinctive attributes, including convenience and flexibility, and incorporates various technological tools that can empower students to engage in independent learning. According to Bali and Liu (2018), students express satisfaction with online learning due to technological advancements. Skillful utilization of technology greatly enhances learners' ability to access educational resources and information autonomously, reducing their reliance on external assistance. Technology plays a crucial role in facilitating learners' access to a wide range of resources related to their desired topics of study (Chalermnirundorn, 2020).

Independent learning in the 21st century necessitates the utilization of technology to foster problem-solving abilities, decision-making skills, creativity, risk-taking, and interpersonal skills. By effectively harnessing technology, barriers to learning can be overcome, making the learning process enjoyable and accessible, thereby boosting academic achievement. Thai universities have been on the right track in embracing the advancement of educational technology.

Background of the Study

With the World Health Organization (WHO) officially declaring the outbreak of the novel coronavirus (Covid-19) as a global pandemic in 2020, in-person learning faced severe restrictions or complete bans. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural

Organization (UNESCO, 2021) highlighted the disruptive impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education systems worldwide. The report noted that vulnerable learners were disproportionately affected, leading to increased inequalities and worsening an already existing education crisis. Furthermore, school closures have varied greatly, ranging from no closures in a few countries to extended periods exceeding an entire school year. Unfortunately, educational sectors were often perceived as non-priority during the pandemic, with the primary focus being on front-line workers, caregivers, and the elderly. The disruption of academic routines caused by lockdown measures had a detrimental impact on the mental well-being of many students. The challenges associated with completing projects, graduation delays, and fears of contracting the virus significantly affected their mental health (Pan et al., 2020). Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, students were already facing challenges related to mental health (Kaushik et al., 2016). In Thailand specifically, depression rates among university students ranged from 19% to 50%, while anxiety rates ranged from 26% to 69% (Boonvisudhi & Kuladee, 2017). These psychological issues further intensified and worsened during the Covid-19 pandemic (Charatcharoenwittaya & Niltwat, 2022). Consequently, Thai educational institutions faced additional hurdles in providing students with effective online learning environments.

Before the Covid-19 pandemic, online learning was not widely utilized in Thailand. However, with the outbreak, the entire country was compelled to rely on online education, affecting all levels of educational institutions, from kindergarten to graduate programs. Government-imposed prevention and control measures had a significant impact on millions of students. Educational institutions swiftly transitioned to online platforms and implemented synchronous and asynchronous learning approaches to adhere to social distancing guidelines. Nevertheless, the online classes delivered through these platforms were perceived as monotonous or lacking engagement. According to Wangkiat (2021), both students and teachers expressed their dissatisfaction with the challenging process of adapting to online learning. Parents also found it difficult to motivate their children to study from home. Despite the initial promise of online learning providing equal opportunities for accessing knowledge and information, the reality turned out to be unsatisfactory. Technical issues were not the only problem, as students experienced stress and anxiety. Overwhelming homework assignments, a lack of interaction with peers and teachers, and extended periods of screen time contributed to their loss of motivation (Thanavisuth, 2021). The sudden transition to online English learning during the Covid-19 pandemic posed significant learning challenges for students, to the extent that some even joined online protests advocating for education reform.

This research study aimed to explore the lived experiences of students who studied one of the English foundation online courses in the university. Although many studies have investigated this area, limited information was available regarding the challenges and strategies students employ to adapt to their new learning environment.

Learning with Technology

The field of English language education is experiencing rapid transformation. Traditional concepts of education are being replaced by novel and innovative perspectives on learning, teaching, and knowledge acquisition. Technologically proficient students have access to a wealth of resources and information readily available. They recognize that the contemporary job market demands more than just numerical or cognitive abilities. Proficiency in another language, such as English, has become a valuable skill that can contribute to securing meaningful employment or advancing in one's career.

In the 21st century, learners possess a strong awareness of the internet and various technological advancements. Consequently, traditional teacher-centered and authoritative approaches are being replaced by collaborative methods. Traditional methods of assessing language acquisition are deemed insufficient in today's world (Pappamihel and Walser, 2009). As a result, individualized and learner-centered approaches are gaining popularity as they emphasize learner autonomy and cooperative learning (Jacobs and Farell, 2001). Nowadays, individualized instruction is becoming the norm, with learning becoming increasingly student-centered. Moreover, there is a growing trend of student participation in shaping learning outcomes (Pauk, 2007).

Language education extends beyond the confines of the classroom and should continue even after learners leave the educational setting. The current trends in language learning empower students to communicate with individuals worldwide in real time. Technological devices play a crucial role in this process and should be consistently utilized by both students and teachers. Internet connections and mobile devices are particularly popular and valuable tools for facilitating interactions between language learners and instructors, as well as promoting peer-to-peer communication. The field of web-based language teaching and learning activities is continuously evolving and offers exciting opportunities for educators. Teachers can easily create web-based language activities, taking advantage of the available technology in educational institutions. These technological advancements, such as the web, internet, and mobile devices, have significantly reduced the barriers of distance, connecting people from different parts of the world (Sarica & Cavus, 2008). Web-based technologies and robust internet connections open up new possibilities for the advancement of educational technology.

Education in the New Normal

The outbreak of COVID-19 resulted in a swift shift for most universities, transitioning from in-person teaching to online learning environments. Fortunately, a few universities already had established online or blended courses in place prior to the pandemic. However, the majority of institutions were unprepared for this sudden switch to online delivery, leaving little time to redesign course delivery for the new virtual setting. There is a lack of research examining the engagement of students with online learning tools, particularly for those

who were unexpectedly forced to transition from face-to-face to online learning, which may not have been their preferred learning style initially (Millar et al., 2021). Many universities utilize Learning Management Systems (LMS), presenting an opportunity to investigate student engagement through their online learning behaviors. LMS refers to software packages that facilitate online learning, assessment, and collaborative learning. As stated by Lonn and Teasley (2009), LMS are web-based systems that enable teachers and students to share materials, submit and return assignments, and communicate online. Here are some very popular LMSs that were used in teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic as follows:

Google Classroom

Introduced in 2014, Google Classroom offers a blended learning approach that has gained popularity in education. As part of Google Apps for Education, it provides teachers with a platform to create and organize assignments efficiently, offer feedback effectively, and facilitate communication with their classes. By integrating Google Docs, Drive, and Gmail, this system enables teachers to generate and collect assignments digitally, reducing the need for paper-based materials—a crucial aspect of modern learning strategies. This paperless approach helps students maintain better organization of their files and reduces the amount of physical storage required, as highlighted by Shaharane et al. (2016). Teachers can easily track completion status, provide real-time feedback to individual students, and enhance class communication. The platform allows teachers to make announcements, pose questions, and engage in discussions with students in real time, thereby fostering communication both inside and outside the classroom. Furthermore, Google Classroom automatically creates Drive folders for each assignment and student, enabling students to easily access and keep track of their upcoming tasks on the Assignments page (Chrome Google, 2021).

Canvas

Canvas has emerged as a popular choice in higher education, offering a user-friendly interface and native web hosting. Drawing inspiration from Blackboard and Moodle, Canvas aims to address some of the gaps found in these leading platforms, as noted by Software Testing Help (2022). One of its key strengths lies in facilitating seamless and efficient communication between educators and learners. Setting up Canvas is a straightforward process, and it provides educators with a comprehensive dashboard for offering feedback, integrating different educational channels, and monitoring students' progress. Notable features of Canvas include open API, customizable user profiles, LTI integrations, and collaborative workspaces. Students benefit from the ability to submit assignments and access learning materials through mobile devices, as well as the option to connect their Canvas LMS account with their social media accounts. Importantly, Canvas offers extensive support for third-party integrations. While Canvas is competitively priced compared to Blackboard, it is not considered inexpensive. However, an intriguing

aspect is that Canvas also offers a free, open-source alternative. The open-source version possesses similar capabilities to the hosted version, with the exception of a few paid services.

Moodle

Moodle is a learning platform that offers a comprehensive and integrated system for creating personalized learning environments. It provides educators, administrators, and learners with a secure and robust solution. The software can be downloaded and installed on your own web server. The Moodle project is supported by a network of over 80 Moodle Partner service companies worldwide, ensuring its financial stability (Moodle). Moodle is versatile, supporting both blended and online courses, and offers apps for iOS, Android, and Windows Phone. Similar to other Learning Management Systems (LMS), Moodle allows administrators to upload SCORM packages as course content. However, if you want to include Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) standard compliant resources, you need to utilize an external tool. Notably, Moodle excels in assessment, tracking, and reporting capabilities. Administrators have a range of roles to choose from, including site administrator, manager, course creator, teacher, or non-editing teacher. With over 1,300 plugins available to extend its functionality and a global network of partners, Moodle can be customized to meet specific LMS requirements. However, it is important to note that Moodle, like any free software, has certain limitations, such as not being turn-key and assuming that administrators prefer hosting the LMS independently. In summary, Moodle is a rapidly evolving open-source alternative that offers significant value and flexibility.

Online Learning Approaches

The unexpected arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic posed a significant challenge to the digital preparedness of educators and students worldwide. In response, universities made efforts to swiftly adapt and offer online teaching and learning environments that could effectively facilitate quality education. As a result, a diverse range of approaches emerged, including synchronous and asynchronous online settings for teaching and learning. Some courses adopted a combination of both, while others focused primarily on either synchronous or asynchronous methods.

Asynchronous

Asynchronous learning environments offer temporal and geographical independence, allowing students to learn at their own pace and in an individualized manner, with less reliance on instructors (Xie et al., 2018). This approach aims to alleviate the constraints of fixed schedules and provides learning opportunities through recorded videos, webinars, podcasts, and online training courses. It promotes self-discipline and self-regulation among students, empowering them to take control of their learning process and derive benefits from it. Additionally, asynchronous learning is cost-effective and does not necessitate daily teacher involvement (Lawless, 2020). Since it is a self-guided module,

students can engage with the course materials independently and at a minimal cost. However, there are a few drawbacks to asynchronous learning. Students may feel less connected to instructors and experience a sense of isolation due to limited interactions with peers and teachers. This lack of supervision can lead to procrastination among students, necessitating gentle reminders from teachers to complete and submit their work for evaluation.

Synchronous

In synchronous learning, students participate in virtual class sessions at scheduled times alongside their instructor and peers. These sessions are fixed commitments that cannot be rescheduled. The key benefits of synchronous learning include the ability to ask questions, receive immediate feedback, and engage in real-time discussions, allowing for the sharing of opinions and ideas. However, there are a few drawbacks to consider. Synchronous learning can be stressful due to the rigid schedule, as students are required to be present at specific times. Additionally, it may involve extended periods of continuous computer usage, which can be tiring for students (Perveen, 2016).

Synchronous learning can face challenges due to factors like poor network connectivity and unstable Internet connections, which may disrupt the learning experience and hinder continuous learning. The teacher determines the learning path, but this may not always align with the students' individual expectations or circumstances. Particularly during a pandemic, students may face personal issues that prevent them from participating in online classes according to the prescribed schedule. Therefore, engaging in synchronous learning requires time commitment and coordination between students and teachers. It is worth noting that synchronous learning lacks flexibility in certain situations (Perveen, 2016).

Online Meeting Platforms

The adoption of synchronous and asynchronous learning methods has transformed traditional in-person learning into online and virtual learning. Online meeting applications have emerged as a convenient option for students and teachers to achieve their learning objectives without the need for physical classrooms. These applications come in various types, catering to different needs and interests. Given their widespread use by the global population, online meeting and video conferencing applications have become essential tools for virtual classrooms. The success of virtual classes relies on the availability of software and hardware devices that facilitate connectivity between teachers and students during online learning (Pratama et al., 2020). The necessary hardware equipment for online learning includes computers, CPUs, laptops, webcams, microphones, and internet networks. In addition to the hardware, teachers and students also need to possess the necessary knowledge to effectively use online learning support applications, such as teleconferencing or video call applications like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and others. Video conferencing technology enables users from different locations to participate in virtual

meetings without the need for physical presence or travel. This technology offers convenience and practicality, particularly in real-time learning scenarios. By eliminating the need for travel, it saves time and allows individuals to safely engage in their work or studies from the comfort of their homes, even during a pandemic. Some of the most popular video conferencing apps used by universities are Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, and Webex.

Cisco Webex Meetings

Webex provides a convenient and flexible platform for teaching, learning, and collaborative administration regardless of location or time. Utilizing a software-as-a-service (SaaS) model through the Cisco Webex Cloud, this tool enables video conferencing with support for up to 100 users and incorporates a comprehensive security system. With real-time communication capabilities encompassing video, audio, and data exchange, participants can engage without the need to travel, saving both time and expenses. The scheduling of lectures in advance is also possible, ensuring efficient planning. The platform ensures meeting and lecture security through attendee identification and offers flexible video conferencing clarity options, including Full-HD resolution. Additionally, the versatility of Webex extends beyond education, as it can be employed in various applications such as classroom training, virtual services, remote support, and more. Accessing Webex is straightforward, requiring the installation of a web browser plug-in for internet connectivity only (Chaimeeboon and Namee, K., 2017).

Zoom

Zoom is a versatile meeting solution that operates on multiple platforms and utilizes a cloud-based platform for conducting video and audio conferences, collaborative sessions, chats, and webinars. It can be accessed on various devices such as computers (desktops, laptops), mobile devices, and telephones. Zoom offers a range of features, including chat functionality, screen sharing, annotation tools, a virtual whiteboard, polling, breakout rooms, the ability to raise hands, and participant management. These features make it well-suited for creating interactive virtual classrooms and facilitating collaboration on projects. The free version of Zoom allows for meetings with a duration of up to 40 minutes, and users also have the option to record their sessions for later reference (Reimers et al., 2020).

Microsoft Teams

Microsoft has recently launched Microsoft Teams, a collaboration app that is integrated into Office 365. This app enhances the functionality of Microsoft SharePoint by providing a simplified user interface and introducing group chat capabilities. It is available as a standalone app for iOS and Android devices, as well as being accessible through a web browser or dedicated app on Windows and Mac computers. Microsoft Teams is included in the educational license of Office 365, which is commonly offered at many universities.

It stands out as a unique and user-friendly virtual learning platform, similar to others in its category, as it is designed to be appealing to students and can be accessed on various devices such as computers, tablets, and mobile phones (Nemec et al., 2020).

Microsoft Teams provides an interactive learning environment that offers various opportunities for collaborative group work, discussions, and assignment management (Janes & Carter, 2020). Its features, including audio, video, chat, and content sharing, make it convenient for students to complete homework assignments, participate in quizzes, collaborate on group projects, and record lectures. By facilitating interactive learning and promoting effective discussions, Microsoft Teams encourages interaction and engagement among students and instructors, fostering a peer learning culture (Jodie, 2020).

Google Meet

The Google Meet application is widely utilized for teaching and learning activities. It prioritizes safety and ensures user data remains private by implementing secure foundations and built-in protection features by default (St John, 2020). Its numerous benefits as a video conferencing application have made it popular among individuals in the business and education sectors. The user base of Google Meet has experienced significant growth due to its user-friendly interface, creating a positive perception of the platform (Purwanto & Tannady, 2020).

Summary of Review of Literature

The field of English language education is evolving due to technological advancements, with a focus on learner-centered approaches and the use of technology for real-time communication and access to resources. However, the COVID-19 pandemic necessitated a quick transition to online teaching, which posed challenges for many universities. Limited research exists on student engagement in online learning, particularly for those transitioning from in-person to online formats. Aside from utilizing synchronous and asynchronous methods to ensure continued education, Learning Management Systems (LMS) have been widely adopted by universities, providing an opportunity for student engagement. Popular LMS platforms used during the pandemic include Google Classroom, Canvas, and Moodle. In addition, online meeting applications have become crucial for virtual classrooms, providing convenience and connectivity. Hardware devices like computers, webcams, and microphones, as well as reliable internet networks, are essential for successful virtual classes. Teachers and students need to be familiar with online learning support applications like Zoom and Microsoft Teams. Video conferencing technology enables real-time communication and eliminates the need for physical presence. Popular video conferencing apps used by universities include Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Webex.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adapted for this study was based on Husserl's (1997) phenomenological framework. Phenomenology, as a philosophy and an approach to research, is all about Understanding. According to Polkinghorne (2007), the term "Understanding" with a capital "U" denotes a particular kind of comprehension. It allows us to deeply connect with the essence of a subject, enabling teachers to respond with insight and compassion when developing policies, initiating change, and fulfilling their roles as educators and individuals.

The phenomenological approach enables individuals to describe and understand their perceptions of the world. In the context of this study, the primary objective of using the phenomenological framework is to investigate the perspectives of students who are encountering specific phenomena in their online learning. By delving into the subjective experiences of these individuals, we can gain valuable insights into their firsthand understanding of the phenomena (Husserl, 1997). The researcher will focus on understanding the meanings that respondents say about the phenomenon being studied and creates knowledge through interaction between the researcher using dialogue and reasoning as the primary methods of investigation.

Phenomenology aims to comprehend the real-life experiences of individuals. The concept of "lived experience" refers to the personal knowledge, firsthand encounters, and direct involvement in daily life situations related to a particular phenomenon (Eskandari et al., 2016). For instance, Rosetti and Henderson (2013) conducted a study that examined the lived experiences of adolescents with learning disabilities (LD) from their own perspectives.

Four individuals who had personal experience with learning disabilities (LD) were purposefully selected for the study. Through purposive sampling, the researchers ensured that the participants had direct knowledge and encounters related to the LD phenomenon. The researchers conducted interviews with the participants, utilizing open-ended questions based on an interview protocol. The interview questions covered various important aspects, including school experiences, identity, self-advocacy, and peer support, among others (Rosetti & Henderson, 2013). The interviews were audio-recorded using a digital recorder and later transcribed for analysis.

Rosetti and Henderson (2013) conducted interviews that resulted in a substantial amount of transcript material, totaling 163 pages. The researchers employed the Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) framework to analyze the data. IPA is a method used to gain insights into how individuals perceive and interpret their lived experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Therefore, the study conducted by Rosetti and Henderson (2013) holds significance as it establishes a framework that will be utilized in the present phenomenological research.

Research Questions

In this study, the researcher discovered the key challenges of students in learning English and their coping mechanisms towards difficulties during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study answered the following research questions:

1. What were students lived experiences of learning English online during the Covid-19 pandemic?
2. What were the learning challenges students faced during the Covid-19 pandemic?
3. How did students cope with the difficulties encountered in attending online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic?
4. What intervention program can be recommended based on the findings of this study?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study explored students' lived experiences of learning English online in a private university in Thailand. The participants were students from various faculties and programs registered in an English course in the academic year 2022-2023. The researcher sought to limit the study by gathering data from the participants' experiences and the knowledge they gained from these experiences. This study used the purposive sampling technique and was further discussed in Chapter 3 Research Methodology.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To explore the lived experiences of university students in learning English online, the researcher employed the phenomenological approach. The purpose of doing phenomenology is to closely examine the phenomena of interest and delve into the intricate realm of lived experiences, as perceived by the individuals who directly encounter them (Qutoshi, 2018). In-depth interviews serve as the primary means of gathering data in phenomenological research. In the early 1900s, German philosopher Edmond Husserl pioneered phenomenology as an approach to investigating the conscious understanding of human lived experiences (Wojnar & Swanson, 2007). In this form of qualitative study, the researcher used an instrument that suited in describing the structures of experiences and exploring students' lived experiences in learning English online.

Locale of the Study

The participating university was a Thai private university located in Pathum Thani province on the outskirts of Bangkok, Thailand. The university was established in 1985, with a total of 138 programs: 94 undergraduate programs; 34 master's degree programs; and 9 doctorate programs. This participating university is where the researcher and the

target participants presently located which provided convenience to conduct actual research activities.

This study was conducted to explore the lived experiences of university students in learning English online during the covid-19 pandemic (academic year 2021-2022). The English course is offered by the university's language institute as part of the General Education program. The course aims to improve the communication skills of students to enable them engage effectively and appropriately in international/intercultural communications. During the pandemic, the university utilized the following virtual learning platforms to facilitate the online learning both in synchronous and asynchronous modes: Google Classroom, Microsoft teams, Google Meet, LMS Moodle, Zoom, and Webex.

Participants

Criterion purposive sampling was used in selecting the respondents in this study. The sampling technique, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study based on the characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Purposeful sampling is a commonly employed method in qualitative research to strategically choose cases or individuals that possess valuable information within the given resource constraints (Patton, 2002). It entails the identification and selection of individuals or groups who have significant knowledge or experience related to a specific phenomenon of interest (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Using the technique, the researcher selected 12 respondents from one of the English courses registered in semester 2 of the academic year 2022. As much as this study desired a bigger sample size, the university imposed limitations following the COVID-19 protocol. The respondents were from the Faculty of Business Administration, Faculty of Liberal Arts, College of Digital Innovation, College of Social Innovation, and from the College of Tourism, Hospitality, and Sports. The respondents in the study had an age bracket ranging from 19-21 with mixed gender and mixed level of English language proficiency.

Instruments of the Study

To come up and arrive at an accurate, reliable, and valuable interpretation of data to be gathered from the respondents, the study utilized a validated interview guide questions constructed by the researcher that entailed open-ended or probing questions allowing respondents to express the nature of the experience they had concerning the statements of the problem of this study. These interview sessions were conducted to bring forth the respondents' awareness of the phenomenon under investigation. Respondents were provided with information about the aim of the study prior to the interviews. These interviews helped better understand respondents' opinions and experiences.

The guide questions used in the interview of respondents were constructed by the researcher. These questions were reviewed, evaluated, and validated by three experts in the field of language and educational management. The researcher designed the questions to facilitate the easy, organized, and systematized collection of significant data. The suggestions or recommendations of the validators were incorporated into the final interview questions.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before gathering the data for this study, the researcher requested the permission of the head of the language institute. Then, each respondent was informed about the details of the research procedures and the required proof of Covid-19 test to adhere to health and safety protocols. The researcher conducted the interview in face-to-face manner and following the time that was convenient for the respondents. All interview data were recorded and saved as electronic file. The recordings were transcribed for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The collected interview data was analyzed using thematic analysis, which involved systematically examining and interpreting patterns of meaning across the datasets to identify common themes. Thematic analysis follows a six-step process originally developed for psychology research, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and reporting (Braun & Clark, 2006). Through this process, codes, sub-themes, and major themes were identified based on the data provided by the participants. To ensure the validity of the themes, the researcher sought recommendations and suggestions from an expert. Triangulation is a qualitative research method that enhances the credibility and validity of data by combining information from multiple sources (Patton, 2002). In addition to conducting in-depth interviews (IDIs), researchers utilized focus group discussions (FGDs) and documentation as additional sources of data to triangulate the findings. In the FGDs, the researcher shared the initial findings from the IDIs with the group and solicited their input and feedback to validate and reinforce the results. Furthermore, respondents provided documents or other materials to substantiate their responses to the interview questions.

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Respondents Demographic Data

Respondent	Gender	Faculty	Major	Years of Study	Age
R1	Male	Faculty of Business Administration	Logistics and Supply Chain Management	1 st Year	21

R2	Male	College of Tourism, Hospitality, and Sports	Culinary Arts and Technology	1 st Year	19
R3	Female	Faculty of Liberal Arts	English	1 st Year	19
R4	Female	Faculty of Business Administration	Digital Business	1 st Year	19
R5	Female	Faculty of Business Administration	General Management	1 st Year	20
R6	Female	Faculty of Business Administration	Digital Business	1 st Year	20
R7	Female	Faculty of Business Administration	General Management	1 st Year	20
R8	Female	College of Social Innovation	Leadership in Society, Business, and Politics	1 st Year	19
R9	Male	College of Digital Innovation Technology	Digital Innovation	1 st Year	20
R10	Male	Faculty of Business Administration	Digital Business	1 st Year	19
R11	Male	Faculty of Business Administration	Finance and Investment	1 st Year	20
R12	Male	Faculty of Business Administration	International Business Administration	1 st Year	19

Table 4.2: Training Schedule of Activities

NEW ROLES OF TEACHERS IN THE NEW NORMAL OF EDUCATION			
TIME	DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3
8.30 - 9.00	Registration	Registration	Registration
9.00 - 12.00	Topic 1: Teaching and Learning Strategies <i>Flipped Classroom</i> <i>Project-Based Learning</i> <i>Collaborative Learning</i> <i>Game-based Learning</i>	Topic 3: Evaluation and Assessment <i>Interviews</i> <i>Portfolios</i> <i>Journals</i> <i>Demonstrations</i> <i>Performance Tasks</i>	Workshop on Lesson Planning for Digital Education <i>Participants apply what they learn from 4 topics by designing a class activity for online learning</i>
12.00 - 1.00	Lunch Break	Lunch Break	Lunch Break
1.00 - 4.00	Topic 2: Interactive Material Development	Topic 4: Learning Management System	Presentation <i>Participants present their</i>

	<i>Slideshows Multimedia Storytelling Video/Audio Recording Creating Animated Pictures</i>	<i>Creating Quizzes Tracking Data Uploading /Downloading Materials Grading System</i>	<i>lesson activities and materials</i>
4.00 - 5.00	Discussion / Reflection	Discussion / Reflection	Closing Program

Table 4.3: Training Action Plan

ACTION PLAN NEW ROLES OF TEACHERS IN THE NEW NORMAL OF EDUCATION						
Program	Objectives	Strategies	Time Frame	Person Involve	Materials/ Equipment	Success Indicator s
Teaching and Learning Strategies	To teach using one of the approaches used in digital education.	Teach a group of participants using one of strategies.	August 2023	Head of the Department	Computers	Participants were able to teach with confidence and able to engaged other participants
Instructional Material Development	To develop a lesson that has interactive class activities.	Create instructional materials using multimedia.	September 2023	Course Developers	Computers	Participants were able to create different learning activities with the use of video, audio, and images.

Evaluation and Assessment	To apply a method of assessment according to the task.	Assess a learning task to achieve educational outcomes.	October 2023	Course Managers	Computers	Participants were able to use appropriate assessment based on the activities.
Learning Management System	To create an online lesson and quizzes	Upload and organize all materials to the learning management system	November 2023	System Administrators	Computers	Participants were able to create an online course with quizzes.

DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 displays the demographic information of the 12 respondents. The respondents consist of 6 females and 6 males, with ages ranging from 19 to 21 years old. All respondents are first-year undergraduate students from various faculties and colleges. They were all registered for the same English course during the same academic term and year.

Out of 12 respondents, 8 are from the Faculty of Business Administration (majoring in Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Finance and Investment, Digital Business, General Management, and International Business Administration). 1 respondent is from the College of Tourism and Hospitality, 1 respondent from the Faculty of Liberal Arts, 1 respondent from the College of Social Innovation, and 1 respondent from the College of Digital Innovation Technology.

All respondents had attended or participated in online learning classes before the Covid-19 pandemic, either as a short course, a supplementary learning activity, or a test tutorial. None of them had studied a full-online course. All respondents expressed satisfaction with their overall intermittent online learning experience, describing it as convenient, interactive, interesting, motivating, and relaxed.

Research Question 1: What were students lived lived experiences of learning English online during the Covid-19 pandemic?

Theme: Description of the Learning Experiences

The COVID-19 pandemic caused an abrupt shift from in-person to online education in order to control the transmission of the virus. This shift disrupted the learning system, as students had to suddenly transition to studying all subjects through a virtual platform. Despite having prior experience with e-learning, the sudden shift to online education affected their motivation to learn.

Difficult

R1-“During the covid, it was very difficult for me to contact my friends especially when we worked in groups. Teachers were also very hard to contact. It seemed that everybody became busier.”

R11-“I had some difficulties maybe because I was not used to learning online. In the past, I only did it as a short course.”

R12-“I had a very bad experience and you could see that in my grades last year. My grades were so low.”

Respondents also described the classes as uninteresting. The previously fun and engaging English classes they experienced became dull and monotonous.

Boring

R2-“I think Covid made learning English online boring. I don't know...maybe teachers and students were stressed out by the pandemic.”

R7-“Learning online during the pandemic ruined my positive expectations. I don't know.... I felt everything was so dry and dull.”

The classes during the COVID-19 pandemic became overwhelming for the respondents. The longer lecture sessions conducted online restricted the movement of students, resulting in physical inactivity.

Overwhelmed

R4-“During the covid, I learned every subject online. I think I was a bit overwhelmed. I stayed in front of the computer or my phone for the whole day. This style of learning demotivated me a lot.”

R10-“My experience was good but not very good. I think I was very tired of studying for a long time in front of the computer.”

Though learning at home provided students with the safest environment during the pandemic, respondents experienced social isolation. They felt that the place where they studied did not have the right atmosphere to motivate them to learn.

Demotivated

R3: "I felt safe while learning at home but the learning was a bit dull. Maybe because I was isolated at home for a very long time."

R9: "During the pandemic, my learning experience online was not that good. I thought that something was missing in the class atmosphere."

Respondents pointed out that learning at home for a long time affected their discipline. Aside from becoming more of a passive learner, they became inactive and sluggish.

Undisciplined

R5: "I lost my self-discipline. I became very lazy. Sometimes, I did not want to get up to join the class, especially in the morning."

All respondents had high expectations for online learning based on their previous positive experiences. They believed that studying alone at home would provide them with the opportunity to be more focused. However, during the pandemic, they experienced a loss of interest and concentration in their studies.

Unfocused

R6: "At first, I thought learning at home would make me more focussed on study. What happened was completely the opposite. I did not pay attention to almost all my classes. I did other things and did not focus on listening to the lecture."

R8: "It's bad because I could not have full concentration. I started to lack interest in studies."

Analysis and Interpretation

The thematic analysis conducted for the research question on the lived experiences of university students in learning English during the Covid-19 pandemic revealed that respondents had negative experiences with online English learning during this time. The researcher identified codes and meanings such as difficulty, feeling overwhelmed, boredom, lack of focus, lack of discipline, and demotivation. These findings are consistent with the study conducted by Thanavisut (2021), which highlighted the major drawbacks of online learning during the pandemic, including the lack of face-to-face interactions with

friends and teachers. The sudden transition to fully online classes also posed challenges for students, affecting their grades. Respondents expressed that it was particularly difficult to collaborate with other students on group tasks. Despite the potential advantages of online learning, respondents felt that their experiences during the pandemic were significantly different. They mentioned that communication with friends or teachers became burdensome, especially during collaborative work.

Research Question 2: What were the learning challenges students faced during the Covid-19 pandemic?

Theme: Description of the Learning Challenges

The restriction of in-person learning during the pandemic had a significant impact on education, leading to the closure of learning institutions to prevent the spread of the virus. All teaching and learning activities were transitioned to virtual mode. Both teachers and students encountered various challenges during this process.

Nearly all respondents faced issues with their learning devices. The most commonly used devices for virtual learning were smartphones, desktop and laptop computers, and tablets. The majority of respondents preferred using smartphones or tablets due to their portability and familiarity. A few respondents only had access to a computer or laptop. However, those using smartphones or computers reported that their devices malfunctioned during class. Additionally, some of the activities or learning materials provided by teachers were not compatible with their gadgets.

Learning Device

R1: "Sometimes, my computer broke down in the middle of the class."

R9: "I didn't have any gadgets needed to complete the tasks. For instance, there were some activities like reading passages or tests that were too small to read on my smartphone. Some websites were also not compatible with smartphones. Sometimes, the teachers wanted students to do the test while the phone camera was also on."

R12: "I used a PC at home but it did not have a camera, so I bought an additional webcam to be able to learn and do the tests online."

In the virtual mode of teaching and learning, having a reliable and stable internet connection is crucial. During the Covid-19 outbreak, it was not surprising that the internet connection became unstable, as all students in various locations were using the same broadband network. This connectivity issue was experienced not only by students but also by teachers.

Internet Connectivity

R2: *"I did not have any problems with gadgets but my internet connection was not stable. Sometimes, it was strong, sometimes, it was weak. It affected my concentration to learn."*

R4: *"My internet and the internet connection of the teacher were very unstable, so most of the time, the classes were interrupted."*

R6: *"I used a smartphone and iPad but my internet connection at home was very slow. It affected the result of my test because the test was timed."*

R8: *"Most of the time, I had problems with the internet connection during the class because I was not the only one who was studying but also my siblings."*

R10: *"The websites or applications that teachers used were not very reliable. Maybe because of the internet connection. It was very difficult for students to navigate. Sometimes, the teacher's internet was also having disruptions so it was very difficult to focus on learning."*

The study environment plays a crucial role in learning, as it can either motivate or demotivate students. One of the challenges faced by respondents during the pandemic was the learning environment. Although all respondents had their own designated learning space at home, it did not make them feel more comfortable or relaxed. Learning at home often made them feel sleepy, particularly when studying in their bedrooms. Respondents mentioned that learning at home made them busy, not with their studies but with other household chores. Room temperature, presence of pets, and interactions with other family members also caused learning inconveniences at home.

Place to Study

R2: *"There were a lot of people in my home, so it was difficult for me to concentrate."*

R3: *"Learning at home was ok but sometimes my parents would ask me to do something. Because I studied at home with my parents, I lost a lot of time attending to my family matters."*

R4: *"I have many pets at home so during the class they came near me and my classmates and teachers would see them in the camera."*

R7: *"I have my own room. But sometimes my folks were talking loudly. Sometimes, they entered my room without knocking on the door so they would appear on my screen."*

R8: "I studied in my room where our house pets had easy access. Sometimes, they jumped in front of the computer screen."

R11: "Learning at home was very inconvenient because it was too hot in my room. At school, the classrooms were all air-conditioned."

To reduce lecture time, teachers assigned work or tasks as requirements during or after the class. These assignments could be in-class activities or after-class activities. Teachers often used these assignments as the basis for formative and summative assessments. Respondents emphasized that teachers assigned a significantly higher amount of work compared to regular in-person classes. Furthermore, these assignments were often given with minimal scoring value and had to be completed within a limited timeframe.

Too Much Work from Teachers

R3: "I think the class work was a lot compared to onsite classes."

R4: "Teachers gave tasks to do every class meeting and the due date was the following day. There was too much class work compared to onsite classes. Most of the time, I sleep late just to finish all the homework."

R9: "There was lots of homework but the scores remained the same."

R12: "Some teachers gave a lot of work. Maybe they forgot that students have other subjects to learn. Every class meeting, there was additional work and most of the students could not finish on time."

For online learning to be effective, it requires full attention from students. It was believed that if students were learning independently, they would be fully engaged in the class. However, respondents described their learning engagement as very passive. Due to the restrictions imposed during the pandemic, traveling from one place to another was limited, leading to most respondents staying at home. This lack of mobility resulted in a lack of physical activity among students. Respondents admitted that they became inactive, with some even being too lazy to get out of bed and prepare for class or actively participate in class activities. Furthermore, the lack of attention and supervision from teachers also contributed to respondents not being fully engaged in the class.

Laziness

R3: "I felt very idle. Most of the time, I fell asleep during the class."

R4: "I became inactive. My score became so low because I forgot to send my work on time."

R5: "I lost my interest in listening to the lecture or doing any group work. I just turned my camera but not actually listening."

R7: "I became less-focus. I felt I was lazy because I thought that there was nobody looking at me anyway."

R9: "I think I became lazy because I did not have to wake up early in the morning or dress up for the class."

Teachers played a significant role in online education. Students relied on their expertise in providing educational content, offering guidance, and conducting evaluations during the pandemic. However, the shift to online learning exposed the ineffectiveness of teachers in terms of educational technology. It became evident that teachers lacked training in digital education. Respondents described that teachers were unfamiliar with the platforms used and encountered compatibility issues with certain activities. The grading criteria were also deemed irrelevant to online learning activities. Most importantly, teachers did not maintain open communication with students for consultations, whether during class meetings or outside of class time.

Teacher s incompetence

R3: "I think the teacher was not fully prepared. Some teachers did not even know how to share their presentation."

R2: "It was hard to contact one another. I needed to wait for 3 days for the teacher to respond to my inquiries."

R5: "My teacher was so strict. I had to turn on my camera all the time. If not, the teacher would deduct points. The criteria was also very strict. I think teachers thought that we stayed at home so we had a lot of time to do what they wanted us to do."

R6: "The teaching style of the teacher was a bit dominant in the class. I was afraid to ask questions unlike in classes held onsite. The teacher also did not ask if anybody had any questions. The class attendance became strict. If you were absent, you won't be allowed to take the test anymore."

R8: "Teachers did not pay attention to my concerns. The teacher just taught non-stop without asking the student if we understood."

R10: "The course management lacked interaction among students. I wanted to have some work where I could meet and talk with my friends."

R12: "Some activities were not designed for online learning. The tests were too long. The camera should be on all the time. Online learning must be flexible and not horrible like this."

Interactions and collaborative activities are essential components of in-person classes, as they support the mental and physical well-being of students. However, during the Covid-19 pandemic, respondents noted that their health was significantly impacted. Their schedules for physical activities such as sleeping, eating, and exercising were altered or adjusted due to the workload assigned by teachers. Respondents described their mental health as poor, as they experienced feelings of loneliness and isolation due to the lack of activities that promote interactions with other students.

Mental and physical problem

R2: "I missed the interaction with my friends because doing group work online was a bit difficult. I did not move a lot. It affected my mental and physical health."

R4: "There was too much class work compared to onsite classes. Most of the time, I slept late just to finish all the homework."

R8: "I had to adjust my time to finish all the work. I lost my time to sleep or to exercise."

R11: "I think my learning discipline was affected. When I studied on-site, I had to get up early and travel to school. But with online learning, I became lazy. My health was also affected."

Analysis and Interpretation

The thematic analysis conducted for the research question on the challenges faced by university students in learning English during the Covid-19 pandemic revealed that respondents encountered various challenges in online English learning during this time. Based on the aforementioned statements, the researcher identified codes and meanings such as learning device, internet connectivity, study environment, workload from teachers, laziness, teacher's incompetence, and mental and physical health problems. These findings are supported by the study conducted by Charatcharoenwittaya and Niltwat (2022), which showed that the closure of schools and public spaces, social isolation, loneliness, lack of engagement, and boredom have had detrimental effects on adolescents' physical and mental health.

These challenges had a significant impact on students' perception of online learning. All respondents expressed that their perception shifted from positive to negative after experiencing online learning during the pandemic. This finding aligns with the study conducted by Nasution and Amad (2020), which revealed that students' perception of online learning was not favorable due to issues related to internet access and teaching style. Respondents also highlighted the lack of interaction with friends and an unfavorable learning environment as factors that contributed to their feelings of laziness or inactivity.

These experiences were also reflected in the study conducted by Khan et al. (2020) with university students in Bangladesh. The analysis revealed that internet connectivity issues and teachers' lack of competence were significant challenges in online education. Despite Thailand being ranked at the top in terms of internet speed in the region, respondents still faced connectivity issues during online classes. The lack of familiarity among teachers with digital pedagogy may have contributed to the stress experienced by students, as highlighted in the findings of this analysis.

Research Question 3: How did students cope with the difficulties encountered in attending online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic?

Theme 3: Description of Coping Mechanisms

The education disruption caused by the Covid-19 pandemic worsened the pre-existing education issues in Thailand. As mentioned in the analysis above, respondents identified the challenges they encountered in fulfilling their academic requirements, which added to their existing stress and health concerns. Consequently, respondents developed strategies to mitigate the negative impacts on their mental and physical health, as well as their academic performance.

During the pandemic, mobile learning devices and access to a strong internet connection became more essential than traditional books and paper. The use of smartphones, tablets, and the internet increased to adapt to the remote learning mode of education. However, many students experienced challenges with unstable internet connections and incompatible learning devices. The instability of the internet often disrupted their learning experience. In order to actively participate in online classes, all respondents felt the need to purchase new or additional learning devices or upgrade their internet packages to ensure fast and stable connections.

Upgrade of mobile device or internet subscription

R1: "I had to buy a new computer and bought an additional internet package. I was lucky because computer shops offered discounts for students."

R4: "I subscribed to another internet package so whenever the connection was weak, I had a spare one."

R6: "I asked my parents to upgrade the internet package to make it strong and fast"

R8: "I had no choice but to upgrade my internet package at home to have a better internet connection."

Regular communication with teachers is fundamental for a strong teacher-student relationship and to improve academic performance. However, learning on a virtual platform made some students hesitant to ask questions or voice their concerns. Respondents found it necessary to use personal messaging apps to contact their teachers when they had immediate concerns. This is not common in the Thai context, as most teachers prefer not to be disturbed outside of class. Typically, teachers allocate time for consultation during or after the class.

Communicating with teacher

R6: "Whenever I have questions about the lesson, I would ask the teacher after the class through a personal messaging app. I talked to the teacher via personal messenger about the reason I was absent. Then, I would ask for a make-up test"

R7: "When I was absent, I talked to the teacher and asked for a make-up test with fewer points."

R8: "I had to talk to the teacher to clarify the instructions."

R9: "I had to explain to the teacher that it would be impossible to do testing while my camera was on because I was using only one gadget. I had to ask more questions or clarify the instructions after the class."

Another strategy that respondents adopted was creating virtual group study sessions. Typically, group study sessions are organized by students on campus for revision or collaborative work. Despite the physical isolation imposed by the pandemic, respondents shared that they were able to join or create virtual group study sessions during this time to motivate themselves.

Joining a Group Study

R1: "I joined the study group after class to motivate myself."

R2: "I did not schedule a group meeting the day after or the following week. I talked with my classmates immediately after the class."

One of the challenges faced by students in online education is the learning environment. Some respondents described their study places at home as unsuitable. They often experienced distractions such as noise from adjacent rooms, weak internet signals, or their own pets. Respondents shared that they had to frequently relocate to different places in order to obtain a stronger internet connection, improve their focus, or minimize distractions.

Finding the best place in the house

R5: "I moved to the upper floor to get better reception."

R8: "I had to put a leash on my pets to restrain them during my class."

R9: "To have a better atmosphere at home, I informed my parents that I learn online. I also used the room away from the living room where my family usually gathered."

During the pandemic, teachers were under increased pressure to accommodate the needs of their students. In addition to their regular teaching responsibilities of lesson delivery, exercise checking, and listening to presentations, teachers also had to address student inquiries. This additional workload added to the challenges of being a teacher during the pandemic. As some teachers were unable to attend to all individual student concerns, respondents turned to their classmates for help. This strategy was particularly used by students who felt hesitant to directly approach their teachers.

Asking help from classmates

R2: "If my teacher is slow to respond to my inquiries, I would ask my classmates first (while waiting for my teacher's response)."

R10: "Whenever I was cut off from the class because of the internet I consulted my classmates after the class and asked them to explain the things I missed. I could not just talk to the teacher because the teacher also did not know how to fix the learning system."

R11: "I usually asked my friends for information for the things I missed."

Internet instability was one of the challenges encountered in online learning. Unstable internet connections not only disrupted the completion of class activities but also caused inconvenience to the respondents. Some respondents had to request extensions for assignment due dates because they could only work on tasks during late evenings or early mornings when there were fewer people using the internet. This allowed them to have better internet access and complete their tasks with minimal disruptions.

Requesting due date extension of assignments, projects, etc.

R5: "If the work needed more time to finish, my friends and I would talk to the teacher to either adjust the activities or adjust the time."

R10: "I had to inform the teacher that the internet connection disrupted some activities. I requested that the teacher give us another chance to re-do those exercises. Sometimes, I had to do the tasks late at night when the internet connection was strong."

R11: "I talked to the teacher to give us more time to finish the tasks."

Students' motivation to learn was the greatest challenge encountered in online learning during the pandemic. Learning from home in front of a small computer screen meant that teachers had limited supervision of students' activities behind the camera. Respondents admitted that finding the motivation to attend or actively participate in class outside of the traditional classroom setting was a daunting task. However, respondents were also aware that maintaining discipline was crucial for online education. They took various steps to improve their physical and mental engagement. Some respondents cleared their surroundings of distractions, allocated extra time for reviewing lessons, adjusted their sleep schedules, and even created a reward system for themselves upon completing tasks.

Improving Learning Discipline

R1: "I started to challenge myself and created a reward whenever I finished my work."

R4: "I removed all the things that attracted my attention away from the class. I turned off my smartphone so I could keep myself away from social media."

R6: "I spent extra time on self-learning to catch up. I tried to get up early in the morning to make myself ready for the class."

R9: "When I noticed that my scores were dropping, I started to manage my time and made up for the loss scores. After the class, I spared extra time to finish all the work. I spent extra time to finish the extra work given by the teacher."

R10: "To keep myself active, I started to get up earlier and made sure that I was mentally prepared before the class."

R12: "I tried to motivate myself by paying more attention to the class. I tried to listen actively and engaged myself to discussion."

Analysis and Interpretation

The thematic analysis conducted on the coping mechanisms used by university students in dealing with difficulties in attending online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic revealed that respondents who encountered challenges were able to adapt to the new learning environment. The researcher identified various coping strategies, such as upgrading learning devices and internet connectivity, maintaining communication with teachers, seeking help from classmates, joining study groups, finding suitable study spaces at home, requesting assignment deadline extensions, and enhancing learning discipline. These findings are supported by studies conducted in Ukraine by Tenreko and Ogienko (2020), which highlighted the difficulties faced during the transition to distance education but also emphasized students' ability to adapt. It is worth noting that none of the respondents in this study mentioned using avoidance strategies, contrary to the findings of a study conducted in Uganda by Ojilong et al. (2022), where avoidance strategies were more prevalent among students coping with anxieties during the pandemic. The analysis of this study demonstrated that the respondents actively employed coping strategies to manage academic stress and maintain engagement in online learning activities. Additionally, none of the respondents mentioned financial difficulties in supporting their education, and they recognized the importance of self-discipline in sustaining their interest and motivation.

This analysis revealed that learning at home in isolation provided an opportunity for students to engage in self-reflection. The challenges they faced during the pandemic motivated respondents to reassess their approach to learning. They recognized the need to adapt quickly to the new normal of education in order to keep up with the lessons and successfully complete their courses. This realization influenced the strategies they implemented, such as purchasing new computers and smartphones, upgrading their internet subscriptions, enhancing communication with teachers and classmates, redefining their responsibilities as individual learners, and reevaluating their role as group members.

Research Question 4: What intervention program can be recommended based on the findings of this study?

Recommended Intervention Program

In the light of the findings of the study, it is recommended to organize an intervention program to immediately address the challenges encountered by learners while learning English online. Since the challenges were mostly caused by the teachers' unfamiliarity with digital pedagogy, the recommended training program will focus on teacher training

consisting of 4 topics or themes as follows: Teaching and Learning Strategies, Evaluation and Assessment, Developing Interactive Materials, and Learning Management System.

The recommended intervention program is titled “New Roles of Teachers in the New Normal of Education” and its schedule of activities and action plan are described in Table 4.2 and Table 4.3.

Training Rationale

The global outbreak of Covid-19 introduced a ‘new normal’ in education. The teaching and learning was heavily adjusted with the utilization of various educational technologies and the adaptation of synchronous and asynchronous learning approaches. These abrupt changes have made traditional ways of teaching, learning, and assessing language acquisition inadequate. Thus, this training is organized to address the challenges encountered by learners while learning English online during the pandemic.

Training Objectives

1. To enable participants to learn innovative approaches to teaching and learning.
2. To enable participants to create engaging and interactive digital materials.
3. To enable participants to understand online assessment methods to achieve educational outcomes in digital education.
4. To enable participants to utilize the functionalities of learning management systems and other virtual learning platforms.

Summary of Findings

The statements given by the respondents in response to research questions were carefully analyzed using the thematic pattern of Braun and Clark. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. In this study, the researcher used an in-depth interview to obtain responses. After transcribing the responses, codes or meanings and themes were identified.

1. The findings revealed that university students' lived experiences of learning English online during the Covid-19 pandemic were characterized as difficult, boring, overwhelming, demotivating, lacking discipline, and lacking focus. These findings were supported by a study conducted by Thanavisut (2021), which found that the absence of face-to-face interaction with teachers and peers was a major drawback of online learning during the pandemic. Moreover, the sudden transition to fully online classes posed challenges for students in adapting quickly, resulting in an impact on their academic performance. Collaborating with peers for group tasks also proved to be a challenging endeavor. Despite the potential advantages

of online learning, the respondents perceived their experiences during the pandemic as markedly different. They expressed that communication with friends and teachers during classes became burdensome, particularly when engaging in collaborative work.

2. The study revealed that these negative experiences were directly caused by the challenges encountered by the students, including the use of incompatible learning devices, unstable internet connection, inappropriate study environments, excessive workload from teachers, lack of motivation, teacher incompetence, and mental and physical health issues. These findings were supported by Wangkiat's (2021) study, which emphasized the difficulties faced by students in learning online from home. Similarly, Charatcharoenwittaya and Niltwat (2022) found that students' mental health deteriorated during the pandemic, significantly affecting their perception of online learning. The respondents in the current study expressed that their experiences during online learning in the pandemic led to a shift from a previously positive perception to a negative one.

This finding aligns with the study conducted by Nasution and Amad (2020), which indicated that students' perception of online learning was negatively impacted by issues related to internet access and teaching style. The lack of interaction with peers and an appropriate learning environment also contributed to feelings of laziness and inactivity, as reported by the respondents. These experiences were also reflected in Khan et al.'s (2020) study with university students in Bangladesh, which identified internet connectivity and teacher incompetence as significant challenges in online education. Despite Thailand's high ranking for internet speed in the region, respondents in the current study still encountered connectivity issues during online classes. The lack of teachers' familiarity with digital pedagogy may have contributed to this stress, as highlighted in the analysis. Although all respondents described their experiences as unsatisfactory due to these challenges, not all of them changed their views on online learning. Despite the difficulties they faced, some respondents still maintained a positive outlook, hoping to find ways to cope with the challenges.

3. The study findings indicate that respondents were able to successfully adapt to the new teaching and learning methods. The analysis emphasizes that learning at home in isolation presented an opportunity for students to engage in self-reflection. Rather than avoiding the challenges, respondents learned how to effectively address them, allowing them to regain their focus and ultimately successfully complete the course.

The study identified various coping mechanisms that respondents used to address their learning difficulties. These included upgrading their mobile devices and internet subscription, engaging in frequent communication with teachers, joining study groups, finding suitable study locations, seeking help from classmates, and

requesting extensions for assignment due dates. Supporting evidence for these coping mechanisms can be found in Tenreko and Ogienko's (2020) studies, which highlighted the challenges and adaptability of students in transitioning to distance education. It is worth noting that all respondents in the current study did not rely on avoidance strategies, in contrast to the findings of Ojilong et al.'s (2022) study conducted in Uganda. In that study, avoidance strategies were commonly used by students to cope with pandemic-related anxieties. In the present study, all respondents employed various coping strategies to manage academic stress and maintain engagement in online learning activities. None of the respondents reported experiencing financial difficulties in supporting their education. However, they acknowledged the importance of improving discipline to sustain their interest and motivation in the online learning environment.

4. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to implement an intervention program that addresses the challenges students face in learning English online. The main challenge identified was the teachers' lack of familiarity with digital pedagogy. Therefore, the recommended training program should prioritize teacher training and focus on four key areas: Teaching and Learning Strategies, Evaluation and Assessment, Developing Interactive Materials, and Learning Management System. The training program aims to provide participants with innovative teaching and learning approaches, equip them with the skills to create engaging and interactive digital materials, help them understand online assessment methods to achieve educational outcomes in the digital education context, and enable them to effectively utilize learning management systems and other virtual learning platforms. By providing teachers with the necessary training and support in these areas, it is anticipated that they will be better equipped to navigate the challenges of online teaching and create a more engaging and effective learning experience for students in the online environment.

Conclusions

This phenomenological study successfully achieved its goal of uncovering the key challenges faced by students in learning English during the pandemic, as well as their coping strategies in the new classroom environment. Through in-depth interviews conducted with 12 selected respondents, this study obtained valuable data for thematic analysis. Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The Covid-19 pandemic has necessitated a shift to online learning, but the experiences of the 12 respondents in this study revealed a negative perception of learning English online during this time. These negative experiences had a detrimental impact on their academic performance. In addition to technical issues and inadequate learning environments, the lack of expertise among teachers in digital pedagogy emerged as a significant demotivating factor.

2. The challenges faced by university students during online learning had a profound influence on their experiences and perceptions of the learning process. These challenges encompassed issues such as the use of incompatible devices, unreliable internet connections, unsuitable study environments, overwhelming workloads from teachers, lack of motivation, teacher incompetence, and mental and physical health issues. As a result of these challenges, the respondents underwent a shift in their perception of online learning, transitioning from a previously positive outlook to a more negative one. This shift in perception highlights the significant impact these challenges had on their overall learning experiences.

3. Despite the multitude of challenges posed by online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, the respondents showcased remarkable resilience and adaptability by employing coping mechanisms to effectively navigate these obstacles. They successfully acclimated to the new learning environment and actively engaged in self-reflection. Rather than shying away from challenges, the respondents demonstrated resourcefulness by utilizing diverse coping strategies to effectively manage academic stress and maintain their active participation in online learning activities. It is noteworthy that none of the respondents mentioned experiencing financial difficulties in supporting their education. However, they did recognize the importance of enhancing their discipline in order to sustain their motivation and interest in online learning.

4. The study highlights the significance of providing teacher training in digital pedagogy as a means to tackle the challenges encountered by students. The implementation of the suggested training program is essential for equipping teachers with innovative teaching approaches, enabling them to create captivating and interactive digital materials, familiarizing them with online assessment methods, and empowering them to effectively utilize learning management systems and other virtual learning platforms. By embracing this intervention program, the quality of online English language education can be enhanced, ensuring the success of students in this new normal of education.

Recommendations

This study represents an initial step in understanding the lived experiences of university students in learning English online during the Covid-19 pandemic. However, it is important to exercise caution when interpreting the results due to the small sample size. To obtain more robust and reliable data, future research should consider a larger sample size with a greater diversity of participants to capture a wider range of perspectives. Furthermore, investigating the effects of stress on the mental and physical health of students would contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the challenges they faced during this time. Lastly, exploring the lived experiences of teachers themselves during the pandemic would provide valuable insights into their perspectives, challenges, and coping strategies. Understanding the experiences of teachers is crucial for developing effective strategies

to support them in delivering online education. Conducting such studies would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the overall impact of the pandemic on both students and teachers in the educational setting.

The findings of this study has offered fresh insights into creating educational methodologies that facilitate successful acquisition of English language proficiency in an online setting, especially in the new normal. Based on the conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The administrators who play a pivotal role in promoting online education, should provide teachers with enough support to implement the necessary instructional changes. With ample support from administrators, teachers can create instructional materials tailored to the students' needs, allowing them to learn synchronously or asynchronously and adapt to innovative learning techniques, resulting in higher satisfaction and achievement levels.

2. Course developers are recommended to develop courses that will teach students a range of skills and knowledge to thrive in an increasingly digital and uncertain world. Students need to be proficient in using various digital tools and platforms. This includes basic computer skills, as well as knowledge of how to use productivity software, collaboration tools, and learning management systems.

3. Academic programs must include contents about resilience and digital literacy. Students should be encouraged to develop their resilience by building a growth mindset, cultivating positive coping strategies, and practicing self-care. The pandemic has shown us that the future is unpredictable and that we need to be able to adapt quickly to changing circumstances.

4. A teacher training program in digital pedagogy is recommended to be organized in short-term, medium-term, and long-term programs, conducted either online or offline. Short-term programs can provide basic knowledge and skills, while medium-term and long-term programs can provide more in-depth training. By providing regular training to teachers, they can gain the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively teach and engage students in online learning environments. This can ultimately improve the quality of education and positively impact students' academic performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher honored and put into account the different sources of information especially the compilation of the interview data. All data obtained in this study was kept in strict confidentiality.

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